

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe

Phase 3

Initial release of catalogue of expertise
and potential service offer

Deliverable D4.1

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D4.1

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ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results

<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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1. Abstract/publishable summary

The ESiWACE3 project offers a range of services, in the form of advice and engineering effort, to the European weather and climate modelling community in order to help make numerical weather and climate simulations more efficient and scalable and to make use of the most powerful supercomputers. Five institutions provide a broad range of expertise available for collaborative projects, providing guidance and transferring new knowledge. A list of service items is compiled that will be the base for calls for applications for the services. The list of service topics covers common challenges in software engineering when dealing with complex codes on high-performance computing in general, and large-scale numerical weather and climate simulations in general, such as portability, efficiency and scalability. The list of service items, together with services from the previous ESiWACE2 phase, constitutes the portfolio of work package WP4 and is published on the ESiWACE3 website.

2. Conclusion and results

This deliverable describes the starting point for setting up ESiWACE3 services provided by WP4. Five partner institutions (NLeSC, ATOS/EVIDEN, BSC, DKRZ, SMHI) contribute with a range of relevant fields of expertise (listed in this deliverable) and ensure that services can be offered to help the European weather and climate modelling community to make efficient and scalable numerical simulations possible on recent and upcoming high-performance computing (HPC) systems.

A list of potential service items is drafted in this deliverable, which can be offered to modelling institutions. The list of topics includes porting and optimisation of existing weather and climate models to new machines, including those with new architectures, such as accelerators, further development of model codes using upcoming techniques to improve the efficiency and performance, such as reduced precision, data compression, and domain-specific languages, and new technology to improve the efficiency of simulation and data processing workflows, such as containerisation.

The portfolio of available expertise and potential service items is also presented on the ESiWACE3 website, and thus potential users can get an overview of the services offered by the project together with practical details about how to access the service calls and other information.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
A1: Transfer and establish knowledge and technology for efficient and scalable simulations of weather and climate across the Earth system modelling community in Europe.	Yes
A2: Close common technology gaps in the knowledge and toolbox for high-resolution Earth system modelling via joint developments across the European community.	Yes
A3: Serve as a sustainable community hub for training, communication, and dissemination for high-performance computing for weather and climate modelling in Europe.	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable
01: Increase efficiency of weather and climate simulations on state-of-the-art supercomputers.	No
02: Design tools to close technology gaps for high performance computing.	No
03: Develop tools to tackle the data challenge of high-resolution weather and climate modelling.	No
04: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	Yes
05: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	Yes
06: Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth system science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	No

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Introduction

The WP4 services offered to the community will be based, and extend, on services previously provided in ESiWACE2. The goal is to initiate and implement collaborations between HPC experts and the weather and climate model developing community in Europe. Within these collaborations, the development, maintenance, optimisation and scaling of models on recent and upcoming computer infrastructure will be supported by guidance, engineering expertise and advice. In continuation of ESiWACE2, the porting of models to accelerator hardware, such as GPUs¹, will be targeted specifically. Furthermore, the scope of services will be expanded to include support for new developments and tools emerging in ESiWACE3 work packages WP1, 2 and WP3.

Fields of expertise

In order to successfully provide services for state-of-the-art methods, tools and techniques, WP4 gathers a range of in-depth expertise in relevant areas of scientific software development and HPC. The partners in this work package cover deep knowledge of hardware architecture and system programming; experience in the development of numerical climate and weather models; porting, optimisation and maintenance of complex codes to/on new computers and infrastructure; and competence in handling the production workflow for climate and weather data.

The WP4 partner institutions contribute the following fields of expertise in detail:

- NLESC
 - centre of excellence for the development and application of research software
 - experts in state-of-the-art computational methods and technologies
 - unique expertise on programming for heterogeneous hardware architectures
 - unique expertise on optimization and auto-tuning of code for accelerators
 - optimising software for supercomputing platforms
 - dealing with extensive Fortran codes from atmospheric physics and oceanography
- ATOS/EVIDEN
 - experienced HPC experts in weather and climate domain
 - HPC applications profiling and tuning
 - heterogeneous systems, memory accelerators
 - access to a wide set of state-of-the-art HPC hardware, software, tools and knowledge
- BSC
 - leading supercomputer facility and software consultancy agency
 - developing and implementing global and regional models
 - data solutions for air quality, climate predictions and their applications
 - profiling and optimising multi-component MPI applications

¹ Graphics processing units used for computations that were traditionally handled by CPUs, for efficiency.

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- dealing with I/O bottlenecks and accelerating algorithms using GPUs
- DKRZ
 - high-performance computing and data management centre dedicated to climate and Earth system research
 - support for code optimization and efficient resource utilisation
 - co-development of ICON especially, particularly its infrastructure, software design, and GPU porting
 - broad portfolio of maintained tools and applications in the Earth system domain
 - data management, analysis, visualisation, and publication
- SMHI
 - long history of Earth system model (ESM) development and coordination of development
 - practical experience of setting up and running climate data production
 - experienced hub of coordinated climate experiments, such as CMIP and CORDEX
 - development of containerisation techniques for ESMs

The combined expertise of these partners enables targeting the efforts and provides the best possible services for the user community.

Potential service items

There is a range of activities in ESiWACE3 work packages that could be turned into services and added to the WP4 portfolio. These include:

Optimising weather and climate model codes

Support to prepare ESM simulations to (pre-)exascale computers by helping to port and optimise model code. Analysis of the computational performance and scalability and optimisation of efficiency, targeting accelerator hardware as well as CPU-codes (particularly for many-core architectures). Also, the assessment of energy-efficiency of model codes can be supported.

Reduced precision for ESM

Support to improve the computational performance of weather and climate models by exploiting reduced precision calculations. This includes advice on implementation options (such as libraries or automated code transition) as well as help to profile and monitor the performance. Developments in WP2 will provide the groundwork for this item.

ESM containerisation

Support the use of containerised versions of climate models. This includes the adoption of containerised model versions for specific hardware and workflows, thereby improving the uptake of European ESMs. This item picks up developments in WP1.

Data compression

Support to improve the performance of model experiments and data workflow with the help of data compression schemes. This activity builds upon developments in WP3, which will use (on-the-fly)

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compression methods well adapted for weather and climate data in order to reduce the amount of data movements and storage and therefore improve performance of simulations and data processing.

Domain Specific Languages

Help to improve portability of climate and weather models by using Domain Specific Language (DSL) approaches. This might involve the application of PSyclone and/or GT4Py, two tools that can help to improve performance portability by representing (parts of) the code in a DSL and ease the transition to accelerator hardware. A potential service activity picks up developments of WP2.

Benchmarking ESMs

Support could be provided for analysing the performance of models by running benchmarks on current and upcoming HPC systems. This might include help with porting to the benchmark system, running a standardised set of tests, and assessment of the results.

Kernel Tuner

KernelTuner is a tool for automatic optimisation of GPU code. Support can be provided to apply this tool to weather and climate models. As a new development, KernelTuner adds support for mixed-precision and tuning accuracy, which comes in addition to the existing functionality of tuning parameters and code optimizations for compute performance and/or energy efficiency.

Optimised I/O or other infrastructure components in ESMs

Support for the efficient use of complex HPC architectures with regard to infrastructure components such as I/O operations, MPI communication, connection of data analysis processes. In addition to the analysis of current problems in existing ESMs, this includes consulting and prototypical implementation of generic approaches (e.g. libraries for asynchronous I/O) and corresponding interfaces in the codes.

Coupling ESMs

Current ESMs usually comprise a number of component models, representing and simulating different physical domains of the Earth system. Exchange of boundary data between the components is often efficiently implemented by dedicated coupler software components, such as YAC or OASIS. The support offered here can in particular represent the implementation of coupled models on heterogeneous HPC systems, where e.g. parts of the ESM run on CPUs, while others are already ported to GPUs.

EuroHPC application support

Computational resources for model development or climate simulations are provided by, among others, EuroHPC, through a competitive application process. Many applications have failed in the past due to shortcomings in the formal-technical descriptions of the requested resources. Support could be provided to groups that go through the EuroHPC application process by offering a simple review of technical aspects of the application, prior to submission.

5. References

n/a

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

n/a

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

n/a

8. Sustainability

The potential service items are in part a continuation of service activities started in the earlier ESiWACE2 phase and the effort ensures that a good level of service activities is maintained for the European climate and weather community, even across funding phases. New service items are initiated by development actions in work packages WP1, 2, and 3 of ESiWACE3. This means that new developments can be turned into services for the community, contributing to the uptake and maintenance of developments.

For those services that include code development, it is specified in the calls for proposals that contributions are to be included in the main line of development for the respective code base. Thus, it is ensured that work that has been done as part of the service is maintained in the longer run.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU).
x	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
x	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The list of potential service offers (the service portfolio) will be published at the ESiWACE website, along with other information about services, including the calls for proposals.

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9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Web publication	Minor restructuring of the ESiWACE service pages and publication of the potential service items as service catalogue.	2023/09/15	general public, specifically European ESM groups	https://www.esiwace.eu/services	unknown

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

n/a

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

n/a